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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Vaccination, a fundamental component of healthcare services and a primary responsibility of healthcare professionals, remains one of the most effective public health interventions for safeguarding community health (Gür, 2019; Yüksel & Topuzoğlu, 2019). In Türkiye, the “Expanded Immunization Program, initiated in 1981 following the World Health Organization’s guidelines, aims to protect individuals and societies from preventable infectious diseases and reduce mortality rates (Turkish Ministry of Health, 2009). Non-vaccinated individuals can hinder herd immunity and increase the risk of outbreaks (Orhon, 2020). This study evaluates the level of vaccine hesitancy and its underlying reasons. The findings aim to enhance awareness and inform preventive health policies.

Materials and Methods: This analytical cross-sectional study recruited all consenting participants aged 18 and older who presented to the Family Medicine Department outpatient clinics at Aydın Adnan Menderes University over six months. The entire accessible population was included. Data were collected using a questionnaire on sociodemographics, vaccination status, and adverse effects associated with vaccines, alongside the “Vaccine Hesitancy Scale (VHS).” Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS 22, with a p value smaller than 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Results: Of the total 318 individuals, 61% ($n=194$) were women and 45.8% had children (mean age= 37.2 ± 15.6 , range= $18-82$). Regarding vaccine information sources, 44.5% ($n=271$) learned from healthcare professionals, while 30.7% ($n=187$) used the internet. Overall, 73.3% ($n=233$) completed adult vaccinations, and 40.3% ($n=128$) completed children’s infant vaccinations. The mean Vaccine Hesitancy Scale (VHS) score was 42.9 ± 15.2 . Among healthcare workers, the mean VHS was 34.4 ± 13.7 , whereas those outside the health sector scored 44.3 ± 15.0 ($p<0.001$). A significant relationship was observed between total VHS score and marital status, number of children, chronic neurological disease, education level, and place of residence ($p<0.05$). Participants informed by healthcare professionals displayed lower VHS scores, while those relying on television had higher scores ($p<0.001$ for both). Adults who did not vaccinate themselves had lower rates of vaccinating their children ($p=0.034$). Vaccine-related side effects in participants or their children were not associated with VHS ($p=0.729$, $p=0.674$).

Conclusion: Vaccine hesitancy is influenced by sociodemographic factors and sources of vaccine information. Individuals’ own vaccination choices appear to influence decisions regarding their children. Misinformation from non-scientific sources heightens hesitancy, whereas guidance from physicians lowers it. Side effects do not seem to drive hesitancy. Targeting relevant factors during health education programs could elevate public awareness and facilitate the control of infectious diseases.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Vaccine refusal, health policy, vaccine hesitancy

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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